

SVD-ROM: Scalable Reduced Order Modeling of Weather and Climate Data

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Introduction

Problem

- There is a need for **data-driven weather & climate models that are computationally efficient, low-dimensional and interpretable**
- Although **Singular Value Decomposition (SVD)** and **Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD)** can extract low-dimensional structure, they don't scale well to modern geophysical datasets in real-world settings
- Existing implementations often require HPC infrastructure, in-memory operations, and complex workflows, limiting accessibility for researchers working on standard hardware

Our Contribution

- We have developed **SVD-ROM**, an **open-source Python package** to perform SVD-based Reduced Order Modeling (ROM) on large datasets using standard hardware
- We show this applied to T850 from ERA5 at native spatial resolution

Methods and Data

- DMD extends the spatial dimensionality reduction provided by SVD to time-resolved data by extracting **coherent and interpretable spatio-temporal modes and their associated dynamics**
- The dynamics can be extrapolated into the future, enabling the use of DMD for **forecasting**
- SVD-ROM enables the computation of DMD on datasets larger than memory by making use of two algorithms: (i) **randomized SVD [1] with Tall-and-Skinny QR factorization (TSQR) [2]** and (ii) **Optimized DMD [3]**
- For example, we can compute DMD of a 60GB ERA5 slice on a 32GB, 10-core MacBook Pro in under 20 min
- Optimized DMD can handle **noisy data** and **unevenly sampled snapshots**

References

- [1] Halko et al. (2011). SIAM Review 53(2), 217-288.
 [2] Benson et al. (2013). IEEE International Conference on Big Data, 264-272.
 [3] Askham & Kutz (2018). SIAM Journal on Applied Dynamical Systems, 17(1), 380-416.

Preliminary Results

1. Sub-seasonal-range forecasting

- We can train a DMD model on 10 years of T850 from 0.25° ERA5 on a MacBook Pro in a few minutes, comparable to the cost of computing a moving-window climatology
- We can use the trained model to produce sub-seasonal range forecasts almost instantly, matching climatology RMSE

- While the ACC is low, it remains positive, indicating the **forecasts retain limited but non-random skill** over extended lead times

- Forecast spectra match climatology, indicating **DMD is extracting the large-scale, low-frequency variability** that climatology captures
- Spectra remain **stable at extended lead times**

2. Data compression with physics

- A DMD model of 60 GB of global T850 occupies under 1.5 GB on disk, and can be used for data reconstruction and forecasting
- DMD weather models are **sparse** (10 to 20 modes) and encode **interpretable physics**

Conclusions and Future Work

- DMD can produce **compressed dynamical generators of climate data**, with small but real predictive signal, while remaining statistically consistent with climatological baselines at long lead times
- DMD models are **sparse and interpretable**
- SVD-ROM enables the application of SVD and DMD to **datasets much larger than memory on standard hardware** using scalable algorithms and parallel, out-of-core computing

Future work:

- Investigate DMD forecast skill over limited geographical domains (e.g., regions with limited access to compute infrastructure)
- Apply DMD to the anomaly field relative to climatology
- Hybridize DMD with other ML frameworks for data-driven weather forecasting: e.g.: Autoencoder + DMD, DMD + Gaussian Process

<https://github.com/SVDROM/svdrom>